

Exploring the Store Patronage Behaviours among Households with Constrained Retail Accessibility across Great Britain

Jason Tang^{*1} and James Cheshire ^{†1}

¹Department of Geography, University College London

GISRUK 2023

Summary

In this case study, we propose to use a large-scale geo-referenced consumer panel to model store patronage behaviours among Households with Constrained Retail Accessibility. Research has previously suggested that socioeconomic inequalities and retail accessibility are important environmental determinants of dietary inequalities. However, one of the challenges in estimating the effect of food environments is the use of estimated exposure, often quantified by the density or proximity of supermarkets or convenience stores in a neighborhood or defined radius, as opposed to the actual households' consumption patterns.

To explore the utility of our data, we validated the empirical data using a Huff gravity model. Our results found households with Constrained Retail Accessibility were less sensitive to store size and have a sharper distance decay function, indicating that they are more likely to seek for the nearest store due to accessibility beyond their residential address.

KEYWORDS: Shopping mission, Food Accessibility, Store Choice, Food Desserts, Consumer Panel.

1 Introduction

The availability of healthy food options at the neighbourhood level has been suggested as a key environmental determinant of diet Glanz et al. (2005). Households residing in areas with insufficient retail accessibility are often hypothesised to consume insufficient amounts of fruits and vegetables and are exposed to lower-quality food outlets, such as convenience stores Chenarides and Jaenicke (2016). As a result, this has led government subsidies to encourage the entry of grocery retailers into areas with limited retail accessibility and the resulting negative health outcomes.

In the United Kingdom, however, the evidence relating the food environment to individual dietary outcomes is inconclusive Hobbs et al. (2019). The lack of evidence may be a result of the wide variety of methods used to define and measure the built environment and pertinent health and

*jason.tang.16@ucl.ac.uk

†james.cheshire@ucl.ac.uk

behavioural outcomes. Due to the time and methodological challenges associated with collecting individual consumption trips, a number of studies have examined individual diets in relation to their food surroundings (such as supermarket density and proximity). In a systematic review, Lake (2018) found that while some studies have found that living in an area with greater availability of fruits and vegetables is associated with higher fruit and vegetable consumption, other studies have not found such a relationship. This is, in part attributed by the lack of evidence of how far individuals actually travel for food, and the association of its travel pattern to their activity space beyond their residential food environment.

This paper addresses the shortcomings of previous research by utilising large-scale geo-referenced data on consumer purchases. The primary objective of this paper is to determine if there are distinct food acquisition and shopping patterns among households residing in food priority areas. Furthermore, to access store patronage decision, we take an approach similar to Suhara et al. (2021) who used customers credit card activities to analyze how and why these customers patronize these merchants. By applying Huff model as part of a behaviour analysis, we aim to access factors that influence the store patronage behaviour among households with constrained retail accessibility.

2 Data and Methodology

2.1 Data

This study’s data were derived from the Kantar WorldPanel survey, which continuously collects and monitors transaction records from a nationally representative sample of households. Our analysis focuses specifically on the In-Home panel, in which participants were asked to record all food and grocery purchases from all retail outlets for consumption at home. This panel contains approximately 8 million transaction records from 33,591 households in the United Kingdom from 2017 to 2018. In addition, we were provided with metadata for each product, household, and retail establishment. Each shopping trip is associated with the retail chain where the household shopped. It is essential to note that the precise locations of these retail stores are not included in the data.

For store locations, we utilized the Geolytix Supermarket Retail Points, which includes information on UK retailers’ coordinates, size, and characteristics. This analysis focused on 20 retailers, including supermarkets chains and their affiliated convenience stores (such as Tesco Express and Little Waitrose) across Great Britain ¹. We calculated the haversine distance from each postcode sector centroid to the most granular store name. The coordinates and distance to stores were then matched with transaction records and other data sources for households.

For measuring the food environment, Priority Places for Food Index developed by the Consumer Data Research Centre (CDRC) was used. This is a composite index that combines data across seven different dimensions related to food insecurity for the four nations in the UK, including socio-economic barriers, retail provision, and accessibility to non-supermarket and online options. In this study, we used the composite indices to classify households living in the most prioritized

¹The list of retailers includes Aldi, Asda, Asda Supermarket, Co-op, Costco, Iceland, Lidl, Waitrose, Little Waitrose, M&S Simply Food, M&S, Morrisons, Sainsbury, Sainsbury’s Local, Tesco, Tesco Express, Tesco Extra, Tesco Metro, Spar, and Farmfoods.

neighborhoods (decile 1) and the least prioritized neighborhoods (decile 10). To link postal sector-level data to the Food Index at the LSOA level, we assigned each household to an LSOA using the population-weighted centroid of the postcode sector.

2.2 Method - estimating store patronage probabilities using Huff Model

To assess whether physical proximity and retail attributes can adequately represent household’s patronage decision, we validated our empirical data with a Huff model. The Huff model calculates distance-based probabilities of people from at each origin patronising each retail destination in the data set. The probability (P_{ij}) that a household at postcode sector i whose to shop a store j is calculated as follows:

$$P_{ij} = \frac{C_j \cdot D_{ij}^{-\beta}}{\sum_{j' \in c(i)} C_{j'} \cdot D_{ij'}} \quad (1)$$

where D_{ij} is the distance travel between i and j , β is the distance impedance coefficient, $c(i)$ denotes the set of store that household i could potentially visit, and C_j is the attractiveness measures of a store j . The attractiveness ² of a store was measured by the exponential functions of store size and market share ³. The Huff model was fitted to the all the consumption trips from the most and the least prioritised neighbourhoods.

3 Results

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

In total, 5.1 million transactions were geocoded with a subset of 20 retailers from Geolytix retail points. Of the 16,490 Geolytix retail points in Great Britain (GB), approximately 12,170 retail points were identified by the In-Home panel with active transaction history. Among the retail points that cannot be geocoded, around 57% were a mixture of smaller retailers that were not captured by the In-home panel and retailers that were not included in the Geolytix retail points, while the remaining 43% were the 20 retailers with absence of transactions from the In-home panel.

As depicted in Figure 1, our analysis shows a some variation in expenses based on store choice and product type. The greatest variation is observed among store types. For households in the most food prioritized areas, discount shops make up 31% of total expenditure, while for households in the least food prioritized areas, they make up only 21%. Some slight variations can be seen in Fruit and Vegetable consumption, although the absolute difference is less than 1%. Furthermore, the distance

²Attractiveness were measured with the series of power functions of attractiveness indicators

$$C_j = \prod_{h=1}^H A_{hj}^{\gamma_h} \quad (2)$$

³We approximated the revenue of the retailer made by all customers

travelled were slightly higher for household in the most food deprived, despite the difference was not salient when disaggregated by the store type (Table 1).

Median (IQR)	Decile 1 N = 3,262	Decile 10 N = 2,818	Full Sample N = 32,194
Distance to store (km)	4.4 (6.2)	3.9 (6.2)	4.0 (7.8)
Distance by store type (km)			
Convenience Store	2.8 (4.0)	1.7 (3.0)	2.5 (4.7)
Discounters	3.2 (3.2)	3.4 (4.1)	3.3 (4.5)
Supermarket	5.3 (7.2)	4.9 (7.3)	5.6 (9.2)
Number of unique store visited per household	13 (11)	11(10)	12 (11)
Netspend per trip (£)	23.9 (19)	27.4 (21.1)	25.3 (20.4)
Number of items purchased per trips	13 (7)	13(7)	13 (7)

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for decile 1, decile 10 and full sample households

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: Expenditure distribution by (a) store type (b) product type

3.2 Global Model Results

From Table 2, regression results showed that different subgroups exhibited significantly different store patronage behaviours. Households in areas with the lowest Food priority Index were more sensitive to distance, indicating that they are severely constrained by commuting costs and seek out the closest stores. Comparatively, households in areas with the least food priority were less sensitive to distance, which may be attributable to their greater ability to commute (e.g. car owner ships). Moreover, we discovered that households in the lowest decile were completely insensitive to store size, which may be a result of their lack of exposure to various types of stores. In contrast, the effect of store size on those with the highest decile was highly significant. In terms of market share, we discovered that food-deprived households have the highest coefficient, indicating a greater propensity to patronise retailers with the largest economic presence (e.g. Big four).

	Decile 1	Decile 10	GB
Intercept	7.589e-18**	-5.031e-17**	1.323e-17**
distance	-1.8445**	-0.8167**	-0.8759**
store size	0.0141	0.3784**	0.2059**
market share	2.0433**	1.1298**	1.6171**

Table 2: The coefficients of sub-group specific Huff models

* indicates $p < 0.05$; ** indicates $p < 0.01$. The adjusted R^2 for the the Huff models were 0.31,0.17,0.22 respectively.

4 Conclusion and Future research

The main purpose of this paper is to demonstrate the value of a large-scale geo-referenced consumer panel for food environment research as a case study. Despite the fact that the relative difference in expenditure between store and products was negligible, the estimated huff model demonstrated a significant aptitude for the effect of distance decay and store-level attractiveness on the food priority indices. In addition, the full implications of the effect of restricted retail accessibility are not fully comprehended, as the concept cannot be captured by a universal index nor predicted by the local retail environment. Therefore, future research can investigate both individual and local-level variations when examining the consumption trips pattern across the United Kingdom.

Furthermore, it is essential to note the potential uncertainty associated with geo-referenced patterns. The linking of these data relies solely on the assumption that the addresses provided by the transaction are accurate and that the households always shop at the nearest store, which may not be the case. Despite the fact that a complete list of retailers was compiled, small independent shops (such as butcher shops) cannot be reflected actively in the analysis.

Nonetheless, a significant benefit of consumer data is that it permits us to analyse trends at both the household and aggregate levels. Detailed analyses of daily activity patterns at the level of the individual in a consumer panel have the potential to be useful in a variety of contexts. Human activity spaces research (i.e., the choice of routes, the choice of stores through time and space that individuals take to fulfil their daily obligations) has important applications not only for comprehending travel and commuting behaviours, but also for planning decisions and policies from a demand-side perspective.

5 Acknowledgements

This work is funded by the UK ESRC Consumer Data Research Centre (CDRC). We would like to thank the Kantar WorldPanel for providing data for this project.

6 Biography

Jason Tang is a PhD student at University College London, department of Geography.

James Cheshire is Professor of Geographic Information and Cartography at University College London

7 References

References

- Chenarides, L. & Jaenicke, E. C. (2016). Store Choice and Consumer Behavior in Food Deserts: An Empirical Application of the Distance Metric Method.
- Glanz, K., Sallis, J. F., Saelens, B. E., & Frank, L. D. (2005). Healthy Nutrition Environments: Concepts and Measures. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 19(5), 330–333, <https://doi.org/10.4278/0890-1171-19.5.330> <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.4278/0890-1171-19.5.330>.
- Hobbs, M., Green, A., M., Wilkins, E., Lamb, K., McKenna, J., & Griffiths, C. (2019). Associations between food environment typologies and body mass index: Evidence from Yorkshire, England. *Social Science & Medicine*, 239, 112528, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2019.112528> <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0277953619305222>.
- Lake, A. A. (2018). Neighbourhood food environments: food choice, foodscapes and planning for health. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 77(3), 239–246, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0029665118000022> https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S0029665118000022/type/journal_article.
- Suhara, Y., Bahrami, M., Bozkaya, B., & Pentland, A. (2021). Validating Gravity-Based Market Share Models Using Large-Scale Transactional Data. *Big Data*, 9(3), 188–202, <https://doi.org/10.1089/big.2020.0161> <https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/10.1089/big.2020.0161>.

8 Data Sources

The data for this research have been provided by the Consumer Data Research Centre (CDRC), an ESRC Data Investment. Funding references ES/L011840/1; ES/L011891/1. The Priority Places for Food Index was developed by the CDRC at the University of Leeds in collaboration with Which?

Geolytix Supermarket retail point (2017) UK supermarket retail point dataset. Downloaded from <https://geolytix.com/blog/supermarket-retail-points/> [accessed January 2023]